

Table S1: Sample sizes of individual male *Gryllus bimaculatus* adult crickets used for each analysis and treatment of the lifelong ALAN experiment. Each column represents another set of analysis on stridulation (left part) or locomotion (right part) behavior. Patterns & percentages include all experimental animals. For the period and acrophase analysis, sample size includes only animals, which period analysis was found significant, hence, all individuals with a synchronized or free-run pattern (but no arrhythmic results). The sample size for the correlation included only individuals, for each both, stridulation and locomotion period results were obtained from the same animal.

	Stridulation		Locomotion		Stridulation and locomotion
Treatment	N total	Rhythmic animals only	N total	Rhythmic animals only	Correlation (only same individuals)
LD	15	15	11	11	10
LL₂	20	19	25	25	19
LL₅	20	19	17	13	10
LL	21	17	40	24	10